

Exploring New Approach With Open Source EDA Tools

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Abstract—In the evolving world of electronics, the imperative for rapid and cost-effective prototyping of Integrated Circuits (ICs) is essential. This research addresses this need through a new approach – the translation of C code into a Graphic Database System II (GDSII) file, ready for manufacturing, using the first fabricable open source Process Design Kits (PDK) SKY130A and GF180MCUC. The methodology involves the use of *Panda Bambu High-Level Synthesis* (HLS) for the conversion of C into Register Transfer Level (RTL). Subsequently, *OpenLane* is employed to generate the GDSII, while integration with Caravel facilitates seamless manufacturing on a 130nm or 180nm scale through the Multi Project Wafer (MPW) programs offered by *Efabless*. This approach not only streamlines the prototyping process but also underscores the potential of open source tools in revolutionizing Electronic Design Automation (EDA) and exposing current manufacturing costs with open source PDKs. As a result, matrix multipliers, data ordering, convolutions, matrix transpositions, Secure Hash Algorithms (SHA), Sharpen filter, Laplacian filter, and Sobel filter were implemented at the layout level.

Index Terms—ChipIgnite, Electronics, Electronic Design Automation (EDA), High-Level Synthesis (HLS), Integrated Circuits (ICs), Multi-Project Wafer (MPW), Open Multi Project Wafer (OpenMPW), OpenLane, Register Transfer Level (RTL).

I. INTRODUCTION

Multi Project Wafer (MPW) shuttles serve as a strategic gateway for Integrated Circuit (IC) designers, allowing them to synergistically share both mask and wafer fabrication costs. This collaborative approach significantly drives down expenses and accelerates the prototype development process [1], [2]. Because of these distinct advantages, MPW has gained popularity and is now widely embraced for IC fabrication, especially in scenarios involving rapid prototyping, academic research, and low-volume IC production [3]–[5].

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Since its inception in 1981, *Metal Oxide Semiconductor Implementation Service (MOSIS)* has positioned itself as a pioneer in the area of MPW services, processing orders with foundry design sizes that comes from a compact 4mm² to a more expansive 25mm². Notably, their technological partnerships encompass industry giants like *Taiwan Semiconductor Manufacturing Company (TSMC)* with whom they work on 12nm and larger designs, and *Intel*, focusing on the 22nm and 16nm spectrum. Financially, it's essential to note that the baseline cost for a project stands at \$25,000. Additionally, there is an upfront charge of \$10,000 per registration, levied on the inaugural order. A point of consideration for academia and prototyping is the constrained opportunity for complimentary fabrication rounds. Given that foundries typically have their MPW rounds fully scheduled and occupied, *MOSIS* faces challenges in carving out additional space on the grid to extend free fabrication offers to universities [6], [7].

Meanwhile, *EUROPRACTICE*, operational since 1995, emerges as another pivotal player in the MPW service sector. Their technological portfolio is vast, accommodating designs that range from an older 0.35 μ m down to a cutting-edge 12nm. The floor limit for their design areas is set at 5.5mm². The pricing spectrum they offer is broad, starting as low as €640 and climbing up to €29,400 per mm², the pricing and minimal areas are intricately tied to the chosen technology [8].

Efabless MPW has gained popularity due to its cost-effective chip creation platform, with cost of \$9,750 per 10mm², which guides users from design to tangible silicon chips. With an active community of over 4,000 chip designers, *Efabless* helps turn innovative ideas into market-ready products. Despite the financial and complex challenges in the silicon fabrication sector, including the high costs of commercial tools and the need for legal agreements for foundry technology, *Efabless* offers a streamlined solution. [9], [10].

As a solution, *Efabless* introduced *OpenMPW* and *ChipIgnite*, free and fee-based shuttle programs, with *Caravel* serving as a template for System On Chip (SoC) designs [10]. *Caravel* features a RISC-V microcontroller, 10mm² space for user’s Intellectual Property (IP) designs, and can be manufactured with 130nm and 180nm technology. The Register Transfer Level (RTL) to Graphic Database System II (GDSII) flow, the layout design process, is supported by the free *OpenLane* tool, based on *OpenROAD*, which is compatible with the SKY130A and GF180MCUC Process Design Kits (PDK) without any cost or legal agreements [11].

OpenLane streamlines the transition from RTL to GDSII, but RTL file design is still an arduous task. Constructing these designs in Hardware Description Language (HDL) mandates an intricate understanding of the hardware, making the process both time-consuming and requiring specialized knowledge.

High-Level Synthesis (HLS) significantly reduces the time required for HDL coding. Instead of laboriously describing the hardware on a low-level, HLS allows developers to express their applications behaviorally, abstracting away implementation details like timing, interface specifics, and memory elements. These details are determined using an HLS tool that takes the behavioral description as input [12].

Although the concept of HLS originated in the 1970s and 1980s, its adoption in industry only became widespread at the turn of the century [13]. Initially, HLS faced slow acceptance due to relatively poor quality of results compared to traditional RTL approaches. However, recent advancements in HLS tools such as *Vivado HLS* [14], *Intel HLS Compiler* [15], *Catapult HLS* [16], *LegUp* [17], *Panda Bambu HLS* [18], *ROCCC* [19], *Kiwi Compiler* [20], among others, have significantly enhanced quality of results, making HLS a compelling option for hardware development [12], [21]. Table I presents a comparison of various HLS tools, showing their vendors, supported programming languages and the HDL code they generate. On the other hand, table II shows the last update of the tool as well as supported features.

TABLE I: HLS Tools and Providers

Tool	Provider	Input	Output
Vivado HLS [14]	AMD	C, System C C++ , OpenCL	Verilog VHDL
Intel HLS Compiler [15]	Intel	C++	Verilog
Catapult HLS [16]	Siemens	C++, System C	Verilog
LegUp [17]	Microchip	C	Verilog
Panda Bambu HLS [18]	Politecnico di Milano	C	Verilog
ROCCC [19]	UC Riverside	Sub set of C	VHDL
Kiwi Compiler [20]	University of Cambridge	C#	Verilog

This research advocates for the adoption of HLS, having as a main question whether it is possible to use HLS tools to create ICs with recent open source PDKs and tools, if possible, the level of abstraction would be increased by using programming languages such as C for the design of algorithms, which can then be translated into RTL (Verilog or VHDL) files and, finally, into an IC.

To maintain a fully open source workflow and avoid the legal and usage restrictions associated with commercial tools,

TABLE II: HLS Tool Supported Features

Tool	Update	Pointer	Pointer to Pointer	Floating Point
Vivado HLS [14]	2023	✓	✓	✓
Intel HLS Compiler [15]	2023	✓	✗	✓
Catapult HLS [16]	2023	✓	✗	✓
LegUp [17]	2021	✓	✗	✓
Panda Bambu HLS [18]	2024	✓	✗	✓
ROCCC [19]	2014	✗	✗	✓
Kiwi Compiler [20]	2022	✓	✓	✓

this research will use the *Panda Bambu HLS* tool to convert C code into a Verilog HDL. Unlike *ROCCC* and *Kiwi Compiler*, *Panda Bambu HLS* benefits from recent updates and project support, while offering features comparable to those of commercial tools such as *Intel HLS Compiler*, *Catapult HLS* and *LegUp*.

As a proof of concept, the current research delves into the translation process from C to GDSII for a variety of systems. These systems range from simpler tasks such as matrix multipliers, data ordering, and matrix transpositions to more intricate processes like convolutions, Secure Hash Algorithms (SHA), sharpen filter, laplacian filter, and sobel filter.

II. DEVELOPMENT TOOLS

A. Panda Bambu HLS

Traditional HDLs such as Verilog and VHDL are known for their effectiveness but they entail long development cycles due to their low-level abstraction. However, a contrasting approach is offered by HLS, providing a faster and more agile solution for hardware description [22].

HLS operates through an automated process, enabling the generation of synthesizable RTL code from algorithms written in C. This RTL code is commonly placed and routed on a Field-Programmable Gate Array (FPGA), however, since it is described in Verilog, it can be implemented in silicon. The attractiveness of HLS lies in its ability to accelerate the development process, offering a more accessible entry point to hardware design [22]–[24].

Advantages of HLS:

- **Faster Development:** HLS significantly reduces development times compared to traditional HDLs, operating at a higher level of abstraction.
- **Algorithmic Descriptions:** HLS allows expressing hardware functionality using high-level languages, facilitating algorithm translation into hardware.
- **Accessibility:** HLS broadens hardware design accessibility, leveraging languages like C/C++, making it more user-friendly for software engineers.

However, HLS comes with its set of considerations.

Disadvantages of HLS:

- **Efficiency:** IP blocks generated with HLS may be less efficient compared to those created with HDLs.
- **Limited Dynamic Memory and Recursion Support:** HLS is suitable in scenarios without dynamic memory and

recursive functions. Translating function code into logic cells requires prior knowledge of the number of function calls in recursion.

- State Machine Utilization: The use of state machines in HLS may introduce complexities, and the sequential nature of state-based designs might not be optimal for certain applications.

B. OpenLane

OpenLane is an open source automated flow, based on various tools from *OpenROAD* and *Qflow*, that performs RTL to GDS design. Initially, it was used to implement a RISC-V based SoC family called StriVe using free EDA tools and the SKY130A PDK.

Currently, it is composed of over seventy scripts and utilities that can be configured to have customized flows, providing the capability to implement any design with any design technology or PDK. The *OpenLane* flow consists of stages such as synthesis, floorplanning, placement, Clock Tree Synthesis (CTS), routing, tapeout, and signoff [11], [25], [26]

The *OpenLane* flow begins with HDL synthesis where the *Yosys* synthesis tool loads the RTL file and optimizes the design, leading to the creation of a netlist mapped by the PDK. During this phase, design constraints like clock definition and boundary conditions can be integrated, and a Static Timing Analysis (STA) can be executed using the *OpenSTA* tool. Following this phase, floorplanning is conducted. Depending on the scenario, *OpenROAD* tools are employed for macro-related tasks, producing a Design Exchange Format (DEF) file and defining matrix and macro core sizes. Essential attributes like Power Distribution Network (PDN), decoupling capacitors, and potential shunt cells are also outlined. For chip-level floorplanning, the *Padring* tool is harnessed, optimizing core pin positions for improved pad frame and core interconnect placement.

Post-floorplanning, the placement of standard cells and macros is achieved using the *RePlAcE* tool, with a subsequent placement check done via *OpenDP*. The Clock Tree Synthesis (CTS) phase follows, with the *TritonCTS* tool placing clock branches and the *OpenDP* adding necessary buffers. Finally, routing is accomplished using a two-step approach: an initial phase with the *FastRoute* tool, followed by a more intricate routing process with the *TritonRoute* tool. In the concluding stages, the design undergoes a comprehensive set of verifications, including Design Rule Check (DRC), Layout Versus Schematic (LVS), and STA. If the design successfully passes these stringent checks, it is then suitable for approval [11], [27].

Advantages of *OpenLane*:

- The entire flow is configured through a single configuration file.
- Automated flow, requires no manual intervention once configured.
- open source, offering a significant advantage over expensive commercial tools.

- Reduces the time and expertise required to obtain the GDSII file compared to commercial tools.

Disadvantages of *OpenLane*:

- Despite being highly configurable, *OpenLane* provides less control over the flow compared to commercial tools.
- Commercial tools have better time optimization than *OpenLane*.
- *OpenLane* uses more logic cells in the design.
- In terms of power, *OpenLane* is outperformed by commercial tools.

The above analysis of the pros and cons of *OpenLane* is based on various works reported in the literature [11], [25], [26], [28], [29]

C. Caravel

Caravel is an SoC template developed by *Efabless* and built upon SKY130A and GF180MCUC technologies, encompasses three distinct sections: the template frame and two wrapper modules known as the management area and user area [9].

The template is equipped with essential components, including a clocking module, Delay Locked Loop (DLL), user ID, housekeeping Serial Peripheral Interface (SPI), Power-On Reset (POR), and a General-Purpose Input/Output (GPIO) controller. Management Area is a controller that includes a RISC-V based SoC, this management area can configure and control the user project area. The user project area occupies a silicon space measuring 2.92 mm by 3.52 mm. It comprises a set of 38 I/O pads, 128 Logic Analyzer (LA) signals, and 4 power pads.

Advantages of Caravel:

- Modular Design: Caravel adopts a modular structure with distinct areas, providing flexibility and ease of customization for diverse projects.
- Integrated Components: The template comes pre-equipped with crucial components, reducing the need for extensive additional design work and accelerating project development.
- Configurability: The RISC-V allows for efficient configuration and control of the user area, enhancing adaptability.
- Compact Silicon Footprint: The User project area's compact silicon footprint is advantageous for projects with space constraints.

Disadvantages of Caravel:

- Fixed Specifications: The user area has fixed specifications, 10mm², which may limit customization options for certain projects.
- Learning Curve: Implementing and understanding the intricacies of the RISC-V based SoC in the management area may pose a learning curve for some users.
- Limited I/O Pads: The fixed number of 38 I/O pads in the user area could be limiting for projects requiring a higher degree of connectivity.

Fig. 1 illustrates the architecture encompassing the template, management area, user area, and within it the instantiation of an HLS IP module.

Fig. 1: Structure of the Caravel template [6], coupled with the inclusion of an HLS IP.

III. WORKFLOW

After underlining the advantages and disadvantages of HLS, OpenLane, and Caravel is time to understand in more detail how to translate C/C++ code into an SoC. A clearer and visual explanation of the workflow is provided below in Fig. 2.

The process starts with the HLS tool. First, the problem to be addressed and its possible constraints are clearly stated. Using high-level languages such as C/C++, or System C, a detailed description of the hardware to be designed is initiated. Once completed, a specifically designed testbench is implemented to verify the created code, during simulation the output of the RTL code is compared with a C/C++ function, which is the benchmark, if the results match it means that the circuit performs as expected, and the RTL is ready to be exported. If bugs are identified, the code undergoes a debugging process and is rectified as necessary.

After preparing the RTL file, the next step is to use *OpenLane* to perform the physical design and verification. This involves combining specific design constraints [30] along the synthesis, floorplaning, placement, CTS, routing, tapeout and signoff. The whole process is performed using the open source PDK SKY130A and a unique configuration file. If no technology rules have been violated, a GDSII file is generated at the end of this process.

To be part of the *ChipIgnite* MPW, or part of the *OpenMPW*, the integration with *Caravel* is non-negotiable. This essential component not only provides the foundational I/O (Input/Output) ports infrastructure, ensuring seamless communication out of the IC but also enables the combination of our design with a RISC-V microprocessor, culminating in a custom SoC. The integration process is straightforward: it mainly involves linking the input and output terminals of each

Fig. 2: Flow chart detailing the progression from C++ code to SoC. The process initiates with C++ input, utilizes HLS for RTL code generation, then, employs *OpenLane* for GDSII conversion, and culminates in a *Caravel* integration, underscored by the presence of a RISC-V microcontroller.

module to the *Caravel* SoC template, guaranteeing cohesive communication within the broader SoC structure.

A. Panda Bambu HLS

Delving deeper, *Panda Bambu HLS* works by capturing the RTL design's essence using a high-level programming language. The tool then undertakes the critical task of converting this high-level model into Verilog RTL code commonly using state machines.

This transformation ensures adherence to design constraints, fulfilling specific targets on timing, resource utilization, and energy efficiency. Through *Panda Bambu HLS*, a preliminary system implementation report can be generated, supporting over 20 FPGA architectures from various vendors such as Intel, Lattice, NanoXplore, and AMD. Additionally, it can produce reports utilizing the asap7 and nangate45 PDKs. Although these initial reports offer insights into resource utilization and maximum frequency, they are incompatible with the SKY130A PDK, making the reports unsuitable for the current workflow. However, *OpenLane* provides reports on the

utilization and performance characteristics of the implemented systems.

Similar to *OpenLane* and *Caravel*, *Panda Bambu HLS* prioritizes ease of use. To execute it, simply download the pre-compiled AppImage distributions and run the command `./bambu <Path_C_Function/C_File.c> --top-fname=<fun_name>`. Here, *Path_C_Function* represents the file's location in the system, *C_File.c* denotes the name of the C file containing the algorithm, and *<fun_name>* is the function name to be translated to Verilog.

One advantage of *Panda* that commercial tools often lack is the flexibility in selecting and optimizing the C compiler. With *Panda*, users can precisely choose the compiler version using the command `--compiler=<compiler_version>`, where *<compiler_version>* can range from *I386_GCC48* to *I386_CLANG13*, among others. Additionally, *Panda* allows compiler optimizations such as `-O0`, `-O1`, `-O2`, `-O3`, `-Os`, `-O4`, and `-O5` [32], which can significantly reduce code size and execution time. These optimizations can be applied using the command `-O=<Comp_Opt>`. For more details on these commands and others, users can refer to the official *Panda* documentation available at <https://panda.deib.polimi.it/> (accessed on April 9th).

Although HLS provides us with a series of optimizations with different repercussions in the system, the present research is limited to generating layouts of the functions matrix multipliers, data ordering, and matrix transpositions to more intricate processes like convolutions, SHA, sharpen filter, laplacian filter, and sobel filter with any optimization.

B. From RTL to GDSII using OpenLane

As mentioned *OpenLane* is an automated RTL to GDSII flow that uses a single configuration file that can be of type Java Script Object Notation (JSON) or Tcl. The initial constraints when an *OpenLane* project is created are *DESIGN_NAME* which identifies the top module design name, while *VERILOG_FILES* lists the Verilog source files to be considered. *CLOCK_PORT* specifies the main clock input for proper CTS, and *CLOCK_PERIOD* sets the target clock frequency for timing optimization. Additionally, *DESIGN_IS_CORE* indicates whether the design is a core or macro, aiding in understanding its role within the overall system.

When working with macros, additional configurations are added, such as *VERILOG_FILES_BLACKBOX* which lets you include Verilog files with undisclosed internal details (black-box modules). *EXTRA_LEFS* and *EXTRA_LIBS* allow the addition of extra library format files, providing more information about standard cell libraries and the behavior of the macro. *EXTRA_GDS_FILES* incorporates the GDSII file of the macro, aiding in the integration of pre-designed blocks. *MACRO_PLACEMENT_CFG* guides macro placement on the X and Y axis, and *RT_MAX_LAYER* sets the maximum number of metal layers considered during routing. Finally, *VDD_NETS* and *GND_NETS* define power supply and ground

nets, ensuring effective power planning and distribution within the design [30].

In addition to the previously mentioned configurations, we suggest the use of the following constraints as they will give you more control of the final layout and less area usage. Constraints such as *FP_SIZING* for floorplan sizing, *DIE_AREA* for defining the chip die area, *FP_CORE_UTIL* to control the core utilization percentage, and *PL_TARGET_DENSITY* that reflects how spread the cells would be on the core area. In scenarios where a design is compact recommending the use of *PL_RANDOM_GLB_PLACEMENT* and *PL_BASIC_PLACEMENT* can further refine the placement strategy, aiding in achieving efficient layouts.

C. Integration with Caravel

To participate in the *ChipIgnite* initiative or avail of the free manufacturing rounds, integrating with *Caravel* is a prerequisite. This process is performed with *user_project_wrapper* (user area), a 10mm² module which has features such as Logic Analyzer, Wishbone, and General Purpose Input/Output (GPIO) ports. The heart of this integration lies in instantiating “black boxes” at the RTL phase using the *VERILOG_FILES_BLACKBOX* configuration and *EXTRA_LEFS*, *EXTRA_LIBS*, *EXTRA_GDS_FILES* and *MACRO_PLACEMENT_CFG* for configuration and positioning at layout level of the macros. Essentially, the process revolves around creating direct connections between *Caravel* and the *user_project_wrapper*.

Fig. 3 shows a visual representation of the layout integration, in which we as a user can modify the *user_project_wrapper* with the only restriction to not modify the I/O ports of the *user_project_wrapper* which are 38 I/O ports that can be made a direct connection of our system with the external world, 128 I/O Logic Analyzer ports that allow us to connect our system with the RISC-V microprocessor, and a wishbone protocol to send information in serial form.

Fig. 3: *user_project_wrapper* layout is pre-designed and integrated with *Caravel* [6].

The integration of our modules with the *user_project_wrapper* is performed by *OpenLane* but using the *Caravel* repository because it has the specific configuration (constraints) for the manufacturing of the IC. Due to the I/O ports of the *user_project_wrapper* not being modified the rest of the SoC is just routed to the

user_project_wrapper ports and the SoC is ready to sent to manufacture through *ChipIgnite* or *OpenMPW* shuttle programs.

After completing this integration, the design undergoes rigorous verifications to ensure that the produced GDSII is aptly configured for successful manufacturing, this verification is performed locally using the “make run-precheck” command and online by the *efabless* company once the project has been uploaded to the platform.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

To showcase the effectiveness of this new approach with the recently open source EDA tools and PDKs, eight distinct systems were developed, spanning various computational challenges, and implemented in both C and GDSII. These systems include tasks like 32x32 matrix multiplication, 1024-element bubble sort, 256x256 matrix transposition, 6x6 2D convolution, SHA-256, and filters such as Sharpen, Laplacian and Sobel, highlighting the adaptability and efficiency of the workflow.

The utilization and performance reports for each module were generated by OpenLane based on the SKY130A PDK, and are presented in Tables III and IV. The column labeled *Gate Count* denotes the count of standard cells within the design. The *Die Area* corresponds to the overall area of the IC, whereas the *Utilization Area* specifically highlights the space occupied by the logic gates both in mm^2 . The *Max Frequency* is determined by the STA analysis. *Static Power* is the power consumed by a device even when it is not actively switching, and *Switching Power* is the power consumed when transistors switch states from 0 to 1 or 1 to 0 which is when the system is working.

TABLE III: Utilization Report

System	Logic Gates & Flip-flops*	Die Area mm^2	Utilization Area in mm^2
32x32 Matrix Multiplication	3508	0.085	0.0759
1024-Element Bubble Sort	776	0.12	0.1105
256x256 Matrix Transposition	878	0.09	0.0801
6x6 2D convolution	4368	0.12	0.1125
SHA-256	14712	0.64	0.613
Sharpen Filter	20590	0.65	0.618
Laplacian Filter	24470	0.65	0.622
Sobel Filter	24522	0.65	0.622
Filter			

*Counted cells: and, dff, nand, nor, or, xor, xnor, mux.

All the implementations presented in the current research and its reports can be found in the following GitHub repository <https://github.com/Baungarten-CINVESTAV/Exploring-New-Approach-With-Open-Source-EDA-Tools>.

Conversely, the transition from RTL to GDSII was seamlessly accomplished for all the systems, highlighting the efficacy of the adopted workflow. Fig. 4 depicts the matrix multipliers, data ordering, matrix transposition, and 2D convolution.

TABLE IV: System performance

System	Cell per mm^2	Maximum Frequency	Static Power	Switching Power
32x32 Matrix Multiplication	67811	166.11MHz	3.27mW	2.43mW
1024-Element Bubble Sort	16277	220.26MHz	1.28mW	0.57mW
256x256 Matrix Transposition	24277	233.1MHz	1.57mW	0.65mW
6x6 2D convolution	65020	100.7MHz	5.67mW	3.8mW
SHA-256	50017	126.42MHz	25.5mW	16.9mW
Sharpen Filter	54762	113.89MHz	26.3mW	23.1mW
Laplacian Filter	67629	105.37MHz	37.9mW	32.3mW
Sobel Filter	66270	110.01MHz	30mW	23mW

These figures provide a complete visual representation using the *OpenROAD GUI* integrated within *OpenLane*.

Fig. 4: Layout view of the 4 systems. (a) 32x32 Matrix Multiplication, (b) 1024-Element Bubble Sort, (c) 256x256 Matrix Transposition, and (d) 6x6 2D convolution.

It is crucial to consider both the die area and the utilization area, as the die area denotes the entire silicon space covered by the macro, while the utilization area specifies the area within which standard cells can be placed. These constraints are assigned based on the complexities of the design. The systems depicted in Fig. 4 represent smaller systems with a die area of about 0.1 mm^2 , while Fig. 5 shows more intricate systems, such as SHA-256 algorithm, Sharpen filter, Laplacian filter, and Sobel filter, with a die area of about 0.6 mm^2 .

Fig. 5: Layout view of the 4 systems. (a) SHA-256 algorithm, (b) Sharpen filter, (c) Laplacian filter, and (d) Sobel filter.

The correct implementation at the layout level of all the proposed systems underlines the adaptability and robustness of the presented methodology, implementing multiple systems with ease.

Embarking on IC manufacturing with *ChipIgnite* or *OpenMPW* introduces a set of unique challenges and considerations. Key parameters to keep in mind include the platform's limited number of I/O ports and the maximum supported frequency, set at 50MHz. Designers are presented with two layout options depending on their requirements: a 2.92mm x 3.52mm area integrated with a RISC-V processor or a more expansive 3.2mm x 5.3mm space without the processor.

Fig. 6 shows the resulting SoC, which integrates the eight featured designs marked by low-latency performance, 32x32 Matrix Multiplication with pipeline, 1024-Element Bubble Sort, 256x256 Matrix Transposition, 6x6 2D convolution with pipeline, SHA-256, and filters such as Sharpen, Laplacian, and Sobel

V. CONCLUSION

The methodology presented in this research breaks the barrier between the areas of software and silicon with the use of open source EDA tools. The importance of swift and cost-efficient prototyping of IC in our constantly evolving electronics environment cannot be emphasized enough. By transitioning from C code to RTL through HLS, we have circumvented the laborious and time-consuming RTL design phase.

Fig. 6: Layout view of the user area, inside the user project, are the 8 IPs made with HLS, referst to [10] to know more about the Management SoC wrapper.

Utilizing the open source tool *OpenLane* to convert RTL into GDSII format, breaks free from the financial limitations usually tied to conventional EDA tools while also benefiting from its high level of automation. This IC design tool makes them more accessible and attainable for a broader range of innovators, researchers, and organizations, fostering greater creativity and innovation in the field.

This work corroborates the correct integration between HLS tools and recent open source EDA tools with the first open source manufacturable PDKs.

Through the *ChipIgnite* initiative or the *OpenMPW* program multiple systems can be manufactured at 130nm or 180nm with cost-effectiveness and accessibility compared to other alternatives, which costs \$9750 that includes 10mm² for your project, the RISC-V processor and its sub-systems, 100 ICs with quad-flat no-leads packaging, and a pair of evaluation PCB boards to test your IC.

In essence, the combination of HLS software like *Panda Bambu HLS*, new EDA tools like *OpenLane* and *Caravel* redefines the landscape of IC design, an approach that has never been presented before with layout open source design tools and manufacturable open source PDKs has been proved, making it not only more accessible but also more streamlined and financially viable. It not only addresses the pressing needs of today's electronics industry but also heralds a new step in

IC design—one that empowers a wider spectrum of visionaries to bring their innovative ideas to life in silicon.

REFERENCES

- [1] Siew, Shawn Yohanes, Bo Li, Feng Gao, Hai Yang Zheng, Wenle Zhang, Pengfei Guo, Shawn Wu Xie et al. "Review of silicon photonics technology and platform development." *Journal of Lightwave Technology* 39, no. 13 (2021): 4374-4389.
- [2] Selim, Ramsey, Romano Hoofman, Mulham Khoder, Adil Masood, Callum Littlejohns, Douwe Geuzebroek, Robert Grootjans, Thomas Drischel, and Kholdoun Torki. "Silicon photonics open access foundry services review for emerging technology." In *Emerging Applications in Silicon Photonics II*, vol. 11880, pp. 15-23. SPIE, 2021.
- [3] Swart, Jacobus W., and Carl Das. "ASIC design and prototyping for education and innovation with a look on Latin America." In *2015 IEEE 6th Latin American Symposium on Circuits & Systems (LASCAS)*, pp. 1-5. IEEE, 2015.
- [4] Chang, Jen-Hsien, Pei-Ling Chen, Chien-Chih Huang, Guo-Hao Cao, and Ji-Ye Wang. "Alternative dicing solution of Multi-Project Wafer (MPW) by Stealth Dicing." In *2016 IEEE 18th Electronics Packaging Technology Conference (EPTC)*, pp. 277-280. IEEE, 2016.
- [5] Meng-Chiou Wu and Rung-Bin Lin. "Multiple project wafers for medium-volume IC production." *2005 IEEE International Symposium on Circuits and Systems (ISCAS)*, Kobe, Japan, 2005, pp. 4725-4728 Vol. 5.
- [6] MOSIS. "Foundry Service". Accessed Sep 1st, 2023. <https://themosiservice.com/>.
- [7] Tomovich, Christine. "MOSIS-A gateway to silicon." *IEEE Circuits and Devices Magazine* 4, no. 2 (1988): 22-23.
- [8] EUROPRACTICE. "Fabrication services" Accessed Sep 1st, 2023. <https://europractice-ic.com/>.
- [9] Efabless. "Homepage." Accessed Sep 1st, 2023. <https://efabless.com/>.
- [10] Caravel Harness. "Documentation." Accessed Sep 1st, 2023. <https://Caravel-harness.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>.
- [11] Shalan, Mohamed, and Tim Edwards. "Building OpenLANE: a 130nm openroad-based tapeout-proven flow." In *Proceedings of the 39th International Conference on Computer-Aided Design*, pp. 1-6. 2020.
- [12] S. Lahti, P. Sjövall, J. Vanne and T. D. Hämmäläinen, "Are We There Yet? A Study on the State of High-Level Synthesis," in *IEEE Transactions on Computer-Aided Design of Integrated Circuits and Systems*, vol. 38, no. 5, pp. 898-911, May 2019.
- [13] G. Martin and G. Smith, "High-level synthesis: Past, present, and future," *IEEE Des. Test. Comput.*, vol. 26, no. 4, pp. 18-25, Jul./Aug. 2009.
- [14] Xilinx. Vivado High-Level Synthesis. Accessed: April. 09, 2024. [Online]. Available: URL: <https://www.xilinx.com/products/design-tools/vivado.html>
- [15] Intel. Intel HLS Compiler. Accessed: April. 09, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.intel.com/content/www/us/en/software/programmable/quartus-prime/hls-compiler.html?wapkw=HLS>
- [16] Mentor Graphics. Catapult High-Level Synthesis. Accessed: April. 09, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://eda.sw.siemens.com/en-US/ic/catapult-high-level-synthesis/>
- [17] A. Canis, J. Choi, M. Aldham, V. Zhang, A. Kammoona, J. H. Anderson, S. Brown, and T. Czajkowski, "LegUp: High-level synthesis for FPGA-based processor/accelerator systems," in *Proc. 19th ACM/SIGDA Int. Symp. Field Program. Gate Arrays*, 2011, pp. 33-36.
- [18] C. Pilato and F. Ferrandi, "Bambu: A modular framework for the high level synthesis of memory-intensive applications," in *Proc. 23rd Int. Conf. Field Program. Log. Appl.*, Sep. 2013, pp. 1-4, doi: 10.1109/FPL.2013.6645550
- [19] W. A. Najjar, J. Villarreal, and R. J. Halstead, *ROCCC 2.0*. Cham, Switzerland: Springer, 2016, pp. 191-204.
- [20] S. Singh and D. J. Greaves, "Kiwi: Synthesis of FPGA circuits from parallel programs," in *Proc. 16th Int. Symp. Field-Programmable Custom Comput. Mach.*, Apr. 2008, pp. 3-12, doi: 10.1109/FCCM. 2008.46.
- [21] M. W. Numan, B. J. Phillips, G. S. Puddy and K. Falkner, "Towards Automatic High-Level Code Deployment on Reconfigurable Platforms: A Survey of High-Level Synthesis Tools and Toolchains," in *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. 174692-174722, 2020
- [22] S. Sriakashmi and G. L. Madhumati, "A Comparative Analysis of HDL and HLS for Developing CNN Accelerators," *2023 Third International Conference on Artificial Intelligence and Smart Energy (ICAIS)*, Coimbatore, India, 2023, pp. 1060-1065.
- [23] J. Zhao, Y. Zhao, H. Li, Y. Zhang and L. Wu, "HLS-Based FPGA Implementation of Convolutional Deep Belief Network for Signal Modulation Recognition," *IGARSS 2020 - 2020 IEEE International Geoscience and Remote Sensing Symposium*, Waikoloa, HI, USA, 2020, pp. 6985-6988.
- [24] H. S. Lee and J. W. Jeon, "Comparison Between HLS and HDL Image Processing in FPGAs," *2020 IEEE International Conference on Consumer Electronics - Asia (ICCE-Asia)*, Seoul, Korea (South), 2020, pp. 1-2.
- [25] D. Zezin, "Modern Open Source IC Design tools for Electronics Engineer Education," *2022 VI International Conference on Information Technologies in Engineering Education (Inforino)*, Moscow, Russian Federation, 2022, pp. 1-4
- [26] C. S, N. S, E. P, P. P and K. P, "Design of an All-Digital Phase-locked loop in a 130nm CMOS Process using open-source tools," *2022 International Conference on Electronic Systems and Intelligent Computing (ICESIC)*, Chennai, India, 2022, pp. 270-274
- [27] Ghazy, Ahmed, and Mohamed Shalan. "Openlane: The open source digital asic implementation flow." In *Proc. Workshop on open source EDA Technol.(WOSET)*. 2020.
- [28] M. Chupilko, A. Kamkin and S. Smolov, "Survey of Open-source Flows for Digital Hardware Design," *2021 Ivannikov Memorial Workshop (IVMEM)*, Nizhny Novgorod, Russian Federation, 2021, pp. 11-16
- [29] S. Hesham, M. Shalan, M. W. El-Kharashi and M. Dessouky, "Digital ASIC Implementation of RISC-V: OpenLane and Commercial Approaches in Comparison," *2021 IEEE International Midwest Symposium on Circuits and Systems (MWSCAS)*, Lansing, MI, USA, 2021, pp. 498-502
- [30] Flow Configuration Variables - OpenLane Documentation. (n.d.). URL: <https://openlane.readthedocs.io/en/latest/reference/configuration.html>
- [31] Baungarten-Leon, Emilio Isaac, Gustavo Daniel Martín-del-Campo-Becerra, Susana Ortega-Cisneros, Maron Schlemmon, Jorge Rivera, and Andreas Reigber. 2023. "Towards On-Board SAR Processing with FPGA Accelerators and a PCIe Interface" *Electronics* 12, no. 12: 2558. <https://doi.org/10.3390/electronics12122558>
- [32] Title: Option Summary (Using the GNU Compiler Collection (GCC)) URL: <https://gcc.gnu.org/onlinedocs/gcc/Option-Summary.html> Accessed: April 9, 2024